

“Don’t Let Them Get To You”: Understanding the Role of TikTok as a Source of Support for Cyberbullying Victims

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1 Survey

1.1 Demographics

1. What is your age?
 - 18
 - 19
 - 20
 - 21
 - 22
 - 23
 - 24
 - 25+
2. What is your gender?
 - Male
 - Female
 - Non-binary/third gender
 - Prefer not to say
3. What is your job title? (Student or name of your job)
(Open response)

1.2 Experiences of Cyberbullying

What is Cyberbullying?

Cyberbullying is when someone uses technology, like a phone, computer, or social media - to hurt, threaten, or embarrass another person on purpose and repeatedly.

1. Have you ever experienced cyberbullying yourself?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Prefer not to answer

2. If the answer to #1 is Yes
How long ago did the cyberbullying occur?
(Open response)
3. If the answer to #1 is Yes
Where did you go for help?
(Open response)
4. If the answer to #1 is Yes
Did you ever look for advice online? If yes, where?
(Open response)

1.3 Coping Strategies Ratings

Imagine you are being bullied online. You are scrolling through TikTok and you see a video that tells you: *Participants were randomly shown 2 examples of advice out of 6 in this category, using the examples shown in Table 1. They were asked to rate the advice in terms of comprehensibility, efficacy and actionability.*

1. How easy is this transcript to read??
 - Extremely easy
 - Moderately easy
 - Slightly easy
 - Neutral
 - Slightly difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Extremely difficult
2. How helpful do you think this advice is?
 - Extremely unhelpful
 - Moderately unhelpful
 - Slightly unhelpful
 - Neutral
 - Slightly helpful

- Moderately helpful
 - Extremely helpful
3. How difficult do you think it would be for you to follow this advice?
- Extremely difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Slightly difficult
 - Neutral
 - Slightly easy
 - Moderately easy
 - Extremely easy

- Neutral
- Slightly easy
- Moderately easy
- Extremely easy

(Attention Check) Please indicate your agreement with the statement below.

Watching cyberbullying videos on TikTok helps plants grow faster.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Somewhat Agree
- Neutral
- Somewhat Disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

1.4 Support Strategies Ratings

Imagine you are being bullied online. You are scrolling through TikTok and you see a video that tells you:

Participants were randomly shown 1 example of advice out of 5 in this category, using the examples shown in Table 1. They were asked to rate the advice in terms of comprehensibility, efficacy and actionability.

1. How easy is this transcript to read??
 - Extremely easy
 - Moderately easy
 - Slightly easy
 - Neutral
 - Slightly difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Extremely difficult
2. How helpful do you think this advice is?
 - Extremely unhelpful
 - Moderately unhelpful
 - Slightly unhelpful
 - Neutral
 - Slightly helpful
 - Moderately helpful
 - Extremely helpful
3. How difficult do you think it would be for you to follow this advice?
 - Extremely difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Slightly difficult

1.5 Mental Health Advice Ratings

Imagine you are being bullied online. You are scrolling through TikTok and you see a video that tells you:

Participants were randomly shown 2 examples of advice out of 9 in this category, using the examples shown in Table 2. They were asked to rate the advice in terms of comprehensibility, efficacy and actionability.

1. How easy is this transcript to read??
 - Extremely easy
 - Moderately easy
 - Slightly easy
 - Neutral
 - Slightly difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Extremely difficult
2. This person is offering a mental health support strategy. How helpful do you find this strategy?
 - Extremely unhelpful
 - Moderately unhelpful
 - Slightly unhelpful
 - Neutral
 - Slightly helpful
 - Moderately helpful
 - Extremely helpful

3. How difficult do you think it would be for you to follow this advice?
 - Extremely difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Slightly difficult
 - Neutral
 - Slightly easy
 - Moderately easy
 - Extremely easy

1.6 Emotional Support Ratings

Imagine you are being bullied online. You are scrolling through TikTok and you see a video that tells you: *Participants were randomly shown 2 examples of advice out of 6 in this category, using the examples shown in Table 1. They were asked to rate the advice in terms of comprehensibility and efficacy.*

1. How easy is this transcript to read??
 - Extremely easy
 - Moderately easy
 - Slightly easy
 - Neutral
 - Slightly difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Extremely difficult
2. This person is offering emotional support. How helpful do you find this support?
 - Extremely unhelpful
 - Moderately unhelpful
 - Slightly unhelpful
 - Neutral
 - Slightly helpful
 - Moderately helpful
 - Extremely helpful

(Attention Check) Imagine you are being bullied online. You are scrolling through TikTok and you see a video that tells you: Online hate or cyber bullying stems from jealousy or insecurity, or people projecting their frustrations because they wish they had what you do. Please ignore the content of this question and choose Strongly Disagree.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Somewhat Agree
- Neutral
- Somewhat Disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

1.7 Spiritual Advice Ratings

Imagine you are being bullied online. You are scrolling through TikTok and you see a video that tells you: *Participants were randomly shown 2 examples of advice out of 7 in this category, using the examples shown in Table 2. They were asked to rate the advice in terms of comprehensibility, efficacy and actionability.*

1. How easy is this transcript to read??
 - Extremely easy
 - Moderately easy
 - Slightly easy
 - Neutral
 - Slightly difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Extremely difficult
2. This person is offering spiritual advice. How helpful do you find this advice?
 - Extremely unhelpful
 - Moderately unhelpful
 - Slightly unhelpful
 - Neutral
 - Slightly helpful
 - Moderately helpful
 - Extremely helpful
3. How difficult do you think it would be for you to follow this advice?
 - Extremely difficult
 - Moderately difficult
 - Slightly difficult
 - Neutral
 - Slightly easy

- Moderately easy
- Extremely easy

4. Do you consider yourself a Christian?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

1.8 Personal Story vs List of Advice Rating

Below are two different styles for a TikTok video that shares advice on cyberbullying. Please read both and then answer the following question.

Participants were randomly shown 1 example of a personal story and one example of advice in a list out of 5.

Which style of video do you prefer when receiving advice about cyberbullying?

- Strongly prefer the list
- Moderately prefer the list
- Slightly prefer the list
- No preference
- Slightly prefer the personal story
- Moderately prefer the personal story
- Strongly prefer the personal story

1.9 Concluding Questions

1. How often do you use TikTok?

- Never
- Sometimes
- About half the time
- Most of the time
- Always

2. Overall, do you think TikTok could be a useful place for teens and young adults to find advice on cyberbullying? Why or why not?

(Open response)

Categories of Advice	Themes	Examples Used In Survey
Coping strategies Immediate actions or long term behaviors to respond, prevent and mitigate the effects of cyberbullying	Don't respond	Don't respond. Usually, people who are trying to bully you online are just trying to get a rise out of you and they feed off of the negative energy that they produce and the reaction that they get out of people. So simply, don't respond and you take a lot of power away from them. (Video 12, Query 1)
	Block and report	Report the bullying. Social media has a system for reporting any bullying or harassment. They may or may not take action. Next, try blocking the person. I know they can keep on creating fake accounts, but every time they do it, just block them. Just block them. They'll eventually get bored. (Video 11, Query 1)
	Take a break from social media	Take a break. Delete that app, put your phone down. Just just take a break. It can be addicting to argue with people or even to defend yourself, but it takes a toll. (Video 10, Query 6)
	Adjust your privacy settings and avoid oversharing	Change your privacy settings. You can have a private page - friends only. You can block or unfriend people. Don't give those people access to you online. Keep personal details off the internet, your home address, your phone number, your school name. If they go to your school, they already know that, but you know that stuff shouldn't be online anyway, for obvious reasons, but keep that off the internet, because some bullies will take it off the internet and take it to real life. (Video 10, Query 4)
	Confront the bully	You can confront the bully. Now I'm not saying you fight the bully like you was back in school. You can confront the bully and have a conversation with the bully and address the issue, talk about what's really going on. (Video 19, Query 11)
	Reach out to them with love and respect	Try to reach out to them with love and respect, because everyone deserves love and respect as that is inherent and not earned. Most of the time, that goes pretty well. They either say I'm sorry or delete the comment, and it becomes a very teachable moment for everyone. (Video 4, Query 12)
Seeking support Guidance, emotional reassurance, or practical assistance in navigating cyberbullying	Talk to a trusted adult	Don't be afraid to reach out for help. Whether it's a trusted adult, a friend, or a professional counselor, talking about what you're going through can offer emotional support and practical guidance. Remember, it's completely okay to ask for help when facing something as serious as cyberbullying. (Video 9, Query 6)
	Keep evidence	Take a moment to collect evidence. This might include screenshots of harmful messages or records of offensive content. Be sure to note important details like dates, times, and usernames. This information can be very helpful when reporting the incident to appropriate authorities. (Video 9, Query 6)
	Check your state laws	Check your state laws. For example, in some states if someone harasses or cyberbullies a person under the age of 18, they can face up to three years in prison. (Video 2, Query 15)
	Contact law enforcement	If you ever feel that your safety is at risk, contact your local police immediately. (Video 1, Query 1)
	Resources for support	If you need more help, here are some places you can call: Stop bullying now: (U.S.A) 1-800-273-8255 SPANISH: 1-888-628-9454 BULLY HOTLINE: 1-866-488-7386. (Video 8, Query 1)
Emotional support Empathy and reassurance	The bully is projecting their insecurities	I remind myself that what they are saying is not true about me, so it has nothing to do with me. It's a projection of their own insecurities, and I imagine that they're talking about themselves. (Video 4, Query 2)
	Bullying is not acceptable	Cyberbullying is not okay. I am really sick and tired of the bullying. Like it is not okay, it's not acceptable, and in no world is it ever gonna be something that I think we should be participating in, because I don't support it. (Video 15, Query 11)
	Empower yourself	Remember that it's the 1% of negativity that cannot overshadow the 99% of love and support that you receive. And when you do choose to focus on the positive, you empower yourself to rise above the hate. Let that support fuel your passion. Keep shining and sharing your light, because the world needs more of what you have to offer. (Video 1, Query 11)

Table 1: This table (continued in Table 2) presents the different categories of cyberbullying advice and related themes with examples from TikTok

Categories of Advice	Themes	Examples Used In Survey
Emotional support Empathy and reassurance	Their opinions are irrelevant and don't matter	Their opinions are irrelevant. They don't matter. They do not hold space in my head. (Video 3, Query 11)
	Remind yourself of your worth	Take a minute to remind yourself of your worth. Write it down, maybe say it out loud. Believe it. Believe what? I matter, because you truly do. (Video 5, Query 11)
	You have haters because you are making an impact	The way I like to think of it is, if you have haters, then you are making an impact or standing out in some sort of way. (Video 5, Query 11)
Mental health advice Techniques that help manage stress and improve well-being	Set boundaries	It's always good to have a healthy boundary when it comes to a bully, because we're recognizing that right now, in the space that this person is in emotionally or mentally, it's not healthy to have them within my personal space. (Video 19, Query 11)
	Practice self-care	Practice self care. It's so important to take care of yourself when you're getting bullied. Make sure you're eating well, getting enough sleep and finding time to do those things that make you happy. (Video 11, Query 1)
	Check yourself	Check yourself, because regardless, I feel like accountability is important. So anytime a statement is made about me, I always check and reflect and just to see if it's true or not. (Video 16, Query 2)
	Volunteering	When I was cyberbullied, I started isolating myself away from people. I quickly realized this is not the way forward, so I pushed myself to try and get out the house, and found that volunteering was really useful. Volunteering has allowed me to get my confidence back by connecting with new people, and it gives me a safe space to talk about different problems I might have while doing different activities. (Video 20, Query 3)
	Don't take it personally	They don't care about you. They don't even know you, so don't take what they say personally. (Video 7, Query 11)
	Exercise	Consider getting some movement in, because movement is going to help get some of the physical stress out of your body. Exercise is a good way to keep yourself physically and mentally healthy. (Video 19, Query 3)
	Journaling	Consider journaling about how it felt, like what kind of buttons it pushed for you. (Video 19, Query 3)
	Go to therapy	Go to therapy and you can find out why it was hurting the way it was, process it, and then hopefully move on. (Video 19, Query 3)
	Don't reread the nasty comments	Don't reread those nasty comments over and over. We all do it but don't, we all need to stop. (Video 6, Query 11)
Spiritual advice Support through faith and personal beliefs	Keep talking about God	Keep talking about God. Fill your heart with God. Let the Holy Spirit shine. (Video 8, Query 12)
	God's watching over you	God's watching over you, and he's got you, so don't worry about them. Let God take care of them. (Video 8, Query 12)
	Turn the other cheek	Turn the other cheek. Jesus taught us to turn the other cheek when someone slaps us on the right cheek, meaning we should not resist or retaliate against personal offenses. This shows our transformation, mercy, and love for others, and reflects the spirit of the kingdom of God. (Video 8, Query 12)
	Pray for them	Pray for them. The Bible is very clear, he who does not love does not know God. People that are talking to you like this, they do not have a revelation of the love of God. So just pray for them. (Video 7, Query 12)
	Don't allow pride	Do not allow Pride. Pride has two spectrums. One spectrum is I'm better than everybody else. A lot of people think that way and they are projecting their insecurities. And then there's a pride of, I'm not good enough, I'm not. Just get over yourself. You're doing this for God. (Video 7, Query 12)
	Develop a very thick skin	Develop a very thick skin. You're just going to have to but you can do it because you can do all things through Christ. (Video 7, Query 12)
	Have a very deep relationship with God	Have a very deep relationship with God. I have a very deep relationship with God. God is my Vindicator. God is my judge. (Video 7, Query 12)

Table 2: This table (continued from Table 1) presents the categories of cyberbullying advice and related themes with examples from TikTok